

Usurped Funerary Objects – UB-006 as a Case Study

Epigraphic Analysis and UV Fluorescence Examination of a Ramesside Painted Clay Shabti

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Persistent Identifiers

Object UB-006

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Catalogue Entry

Inventory number: UB-006 (Secondary catalogue code: U-512)

Collection: Beckers Collection (Aachen), Section A – Ushabtis and Related Funerary Objects

Short description: Large mummiform ushabti made of painted terracotta (red clay) with a white ground layer and polychrome decoration. The fragmentarily preserved inscription shows clear traces of ancient usurpation; a later owner name ("Jt.f") was inserted within a red rectangular frame. Due to its secure provenance, publication history, and epigraphic significance, the object is of high scholarly relevance.

Date: New Kingdom, 19th Dynasty (ca. 1292–1186 BCE)

Material: Red clay (terracotta) with a white ground layer; details in black, red, green, and blue

Measurements: Height 22.2 cm; width 6.5 cm; depth 4.5 cm; weight 410 g

Description: Large mummiform ushabti made of red clay (terracotta) with a white ground layer and polychrome painted details in black, red, green and blue. The surface shows careful preparation, with the paint layer applied over a clearly visible white ground. The inscription is only fragmentarily preserved and shows evidence of ancient modification. A later owner name was inserted within a red rectangular frame, while the name of the god Osiris (Wsir) is clearly preserved below.

Material observation: The combination of a red clay body, a white preparation layer, and polychrome painted decoration corresponds well to painted terracotta ushabtis of the New Kingdom. The clear separation between ground layer and paint application, as well as the surviving pigment areas, indicate a high-quality original execution.

Date observation: Material, polychromy, and the manner of inscription modification and usurpation support an attribution to the 19th Dynasty of the New Kingdom, in agreement with the published scholarly assessment.¹ The execution of the secondary name panel framed in red is a documented feature of later owner appropriation on funerary objects of this period.

Inscription (overview): Secondary inscription within a red-framed rectangular panel on the front of the figure. The original, nearly encircling primary inscription was erased in antiquity. Within the red panel, parts of the earlier inscription were reused and supplemented with newly added signs. The usurpation has been confirmed by Prof. Hermann A. Schloegl.² Securely identifiable elements are the divine name Osiris (Wsir) and the name of the usurper Jt.f (jt=f, "his father"). According to Schloegl, the secondary inscription represents a short version of Book of the Dead Spell 6; the end of the text is lost due to the break in the lower section.

Published: Schloegl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Aegyptische Totenfiguren aus oeffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zurich: University of Zurich, 1990, catalogue no. 74, p. 135.³

Provenance (summary): Formerly the collection of Hermann A. Schloegl (acquired on 26 Jun 1987 at Lempertz, Cologne, Auction 622, Lot 1647)⁴; acquired on 04 Jul 2025 by Dirk Beckers from Gorny & Mosch, Auction 312, Lot 8.⁵

¹Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

²Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

³Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

⁴Lempertz Auktion 622, Köln, 26.06.1987, Taf. 79, Nr. 1647.

⁵Gorny & Mosch Giessener Münzhandlung, Auktion 312, 04.07.2025, Los 8: "Usurped shabti of It".
<https://auktionen.gmcoinart.de/Auktion/KatalogArchiv?intAuktionsId=1595>

Usurpation as a Phenomenon

The usurpation of funerary objects refers to the ancient practice of reassigning already-inscribed grave goods – ushabtis, sarcophagi, stelae, statues, or coffins – to a new owner by removing, overwriting, or supplementing the original inscription. The phenomenon is attested throughout all periods of ancient Egypt, but occurs with particular concentration in the New Kingdom, notably during the Ramesside Period (19th–20th Dynasties).⁶

Usurpation must be strictly distinguished from the related concept of *damnatio memoriae*: while the latter aimed at the deliberate erasure of a person and their memory – paradigmatically documented in Akhenaten's persecution of the Amun cult or the suppression of Hatshepsut's representations – the usurpation of small funerary objects generally pursued pragmatic economic and social goals without hostile intent toward the original owner.

Mechanisms of usurpation: The techniques of inscription removal and renewal vary according to the carrier material and object type. In the case of painted clay ushabtis, the primary inscription was typically removed by mechanical abrasion (grinding, scraping) or by covering with a new ground layer. A new inscription could then be applied directly to the prepared surface – in some cases reusing preserved portions of the original text. For stone and wooden coffins, replastering and repainting is more commonly documented, as in the case of a 19th Dynasty coffin reworked in the 21st Dynasty for a man named Mentuhotep. In UB-006, the method of overwriting on a painted clay surface is particularly well documented: the original, nearly encircling primary inscription was erased, and the secondary inscription was inserted within a deliberately applied red rectangular frame (see Fig. 1).

Motives for usurpation: The reasons for the reassignment of funerary objects are varied and cannot be reduced to a single motive. Economic considerations undoubtedly played a central role: Kara Cooney (UCLA) has demonstrated in her foundational studies of the Ramesside Period that funerary goods were manufactured, traded, and occasionally reused within an active funerary economy.⁷ High-quality, already-completed objects – particularly those with skilled painting or elaborate inscriptions – could be acquired cost-effectively through usurpation, without the expense of complete new manufacture.

Religious and magical motives must also be assumed: taking over an object already activated for funerary purpose – that is, one already inscribed with the name of Osiris and a correct formula from the Book of the Dead – could be regarded as magically effective or at least as equivalent to a newly made piece. The decisive intervention, as Schlögl demonstrates for UB-006, was the correct substitution of the owner's name.⁸

In some cases, tomb robbery or the dissolution of older burials may also have led to the reuse of funerary goods. Peter Brand (University of Memphis, UCLA Encyclopedia of Egyptology) has noted that private individuals frequently reused tombs and funerary goods – including those of their own ancestors – and that while this practice was morally questionable, it was evidently widespread. The late 20th and early 21st Dynasties were marked by a systematic plundering of the Theban necropoleis, the extent of which is documented by the late Ramesside tomb robbery papyri.

Distribution and frequency: Usurped ushabtis appear regularly in Egyptian museum collections and auction catalogues, though rarely as clearly documented as in the case of UB-006. The phenomenon is most frequently attested among large-scale limestone and faience ushabtis of high-ranking individuals; for painted clay examples with a clearly demonstrable usurpation retaining a frame structure, published instances are comparatively rare.⁹ A well-known example in the research literature is a wooden ushabti in Edinburgh (National Museums Scotland, A.1934.565), in which an earlier owner's name was overwritten with that of Ramessesnacht – a directly comparable case of inscription overwriting on a funerary figurine.

Usurpation in the context of the Ramesside funerary economy: During the Ramesside Period, an active market for

⁶Schneider, Hans D.: *Shabtis. An Introduction to the History of Ancient Egyptian Funerary Statuettes*. 3 Bde., Leiden: Rijksmuseum van Oudheden / Brill, 1977.

⁷Petrie, W. M. Flinders: *Shabtis*. London: British School of Archaeology in Egypt / Bernard Quaritch, 1914.

⁸Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

⁹Schneider, Hans D.: *Shabtis. An Introduction to the History of Ancient Egyptian Funerary Statuettes*. 3 Bde., Leiden: Rijksmuseum van Oudheden / Brill, 1977.

funerary objects existed in western Thebes which – as Kara Cooney’s study *The Cost of Death* (2007) and her follow-up work *Recycling for Death* (2024) demonstrate – encompassed new production and reuse side by side. Ostraca and papyri from Deir el-Medina document concrete sales and commissions for funerary equipment. Usurpation was thus less a marginal phenomenon than a structurally embedded element of this economy: in a society in which the correct personal name and the correct formula constituted the magical efficacy of an object, a carefully reassigned ushabti was functionally equivalent to a newly manufactured one.

Pragmatic reuse at the royal level – KV62 as a reference case: That pragmatic reassignment of funerary objects was not a phenomenon confined to private burials is demonstrated with particular force by the inventory from KV62, the tomb of Tutankhamun (18th Dynasty, c. 1323 BCE). Several objects from this arguably most famous tomb discovery in Egyptology show confirmed or highly probable traces of reassignment: the four miniature golden canopic coffins bear, beneath Tutankhamun’s cartouches, reconstructable inscriptions of Neferneferuaten, including the epithet Axt-n-H(j)=s – “she who is beneficial for her husband” – which refers exclusively to a female owner; the pectoral of the goddess Nut was originally made for Neferneferuaten and altered only in its cartouches; and the golden death mask, according to Nicholas Reeves and Marc Gabolde, bears palimpsest traces of an earlier cartouche pointing to Ankhkheperure Neferneferuaten as the original owner.¹⁰

The decisive motive here was not economic saving but logistical time pressure: the unexpected death of the young king forced those responsible to draw on available material – originally intended for Neferneferuaten – within the ritually prescribed mummification period of approximately 70 days, with barely more than 90 days until burial. The result is structurally identical in both cases: incomplete, inconsistent overwritings in which the iconographic substance of the objects remained untouched and only the name fields were altered. Not the deliberate erasure of a predecessor from memory, but practical necessity explains this finding. A *damnatio memoriae* would have been systematic, comprehensive, and consistent – as the treatment of Akhenaten in the post-Amarna textual record demonstrates.

Despite the fundamental difference in social register, material value, and dynastic context, UB-006 and the reassigned objects from KV62 share the same phenomenological structure: pragmatic reuse of a funerarily activated object under the primacy of the correct owner’s name, without hostile intent toward the original owner. As the best-known tomb discovery in Egyptology, KV62 provides a widely received frame of reference that situates the phenomenon described for UB-006 within a broader cultural context.

The particular significance of the red frame: The marking of the secondary inscription by a red rectangular frame, as documented in UB-006, represents a recurring design device that clearly delineates the new owner area from the rest of the object. Comparable red dividing lines and frame elements are attested as a structuring design principle in painted ushabtis of the 19th Dynasty – such as pieces EA33947 (Pashed) and EA15760 (Hat) in the British Museum.¹¹ Whether this framing in the case of UB-006 was intentionally designed as a signal of usurpation or merely a pragmatic device for delimiting the secondary inscription cannot be determined with certainty; in any case, it survives as a visible testimony to the intervention.

¹⁰Reeves, Nicholas: *The Gold Mask of Ankhkheperure Neferneferuaten*. In: *Göttinger Miszellen* 247 (2015), S. 71–75. [Bitte Seitenangaben vor Drucklegung anhand des Originals verifizieren.]

Gabolde, Marc: *D’Akhenaton à Toutânkhamon*. Lyon: Université Lumière-Lyon 2, 1998. (Collection de l’Institut d’Archéologie et d’Histoire de l’Antiquité, 3).

Eaton-Krauss, Marianne: *The Unknown Tutankhamun*. London / New York: Bloomsbury Academic, 2016.

¹¹British Museum, EA33947 (Shabti of Pashed; painted pottery; 19. Dynastie).

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA33947

British Museum, EA15760 (Shabti of Hat; painted pottery; 19. Dynastie).

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA15760

Historical Context

The Ramesside period (ca. 1295–1069 BCE) was an era of unusual funerary intensity. Under the pharaohs of the 19th and 20th Dynasties – from Ramesses I to Ramesses XI – the production of grave goods, the construction of tombs, and the associated craft and priestly infrastructure reached a peak that is directly reflected in the quantity and quality of surviving objects.¹² The ushabti UB-006 is a product of this world – and at the same time a witness to its shadow sides.

Thebes as the centre of funerary culture

The West Theban necropolis was the most important funerary centre of New Kingdom Egypt. The Valley of the Kings (Biban el-Muluk) housed the tombs of the pharaohs of the 18th to 20th Dynasties; the adjacent mountain necropoleis of Deir el-Medina, Qurnet Murai, and Sheikh Abd el-Qurna were burial places for members of the middle and upper classes. The workers and craftsmen who constructed and decorated the royal tombs lived in the purpose-built village of Deir el-Medina (ancient Egyptian: Set-Maat, "Place of Truth"), a state-supported community with its own internal organisation.¹³

This concentration of tomb construction, craft production, and religious expertise created a dense funerary economy: coffins, ushabtis, papyri, amulets, and funerary equipment were produced, sold, and – as ostraca and papyri from Deir el-Medina attest – also traded and reused. Kara Cooney (UCLA) has demonstrated in her foundational studies that an active private sector existed within this economy, in which craftsmen produced funerary objects on commission alongside their official work. Price records on ostraca cite concrete values for coffins, ushabtis, and other funerary objects in deben weights.¹⁴

The priesthood of the 19th Dynasty and the title *it-ntr*

The social standing of the priesthood grew considerably over the course of the Ramesside period. In the 19th Dynasty, priests bearing the title *it-ntr* (God's Father, ancient Egyptian: *it-ntr*) formed an established group within the cultic hierarchy. The title, whose precise rank fluctuated between the simple *wab*-priest and the *hem-netjer* (Servant of God, first prophet), had been attested since the Old Kingdom and carried a double meaning: it could designate a mid-ranking priest as well as the non-royal father of a pharaoh, or, in a transferred sense, a high-ranking person of trust to the ruler.¹⁵ In the Ramesside context, *it-ntr* is best attested as a priestly rank – thus the later High Priest of Amun Bakenkhonsu, who served under Ramesses II, officiated as *it-ntr* for twelve years according to his biography before rising to the rank of third prophet.

For UB-006, this title is significant: Schloegl conjectures that the first owner of the ushabti held the title *it-ntr* – a man of priestly standing, therefore not of low rank, but socially established enough to have commissioned a large-format, high-quality, painted terracotta ushabti.¹⁶ The quality of the object – its size, its careful ground preparation, its polychrome decoration – is consistent with such a social milieu.

Tomb robbery and the circulation of funerary objects

The reverse side of the rich funerary culture of the Ramesside period was the structural vulnerability of the necropoleis. Tomb robbery was not a marginal phenomenon but a systemic problem that even affected the necropolis workers of Deir el-Medina themselves: the late Ramesside tomb robbery papyri (particularly the Abbott, Amherst/Leopold II, and Mayer A and B papyri, dated to the reign of Ramesses IX, ca. 1126–1108 BCE) document in interrogation records and confessions an organised tomb robbery scandal involving high-ranking officials and temple guards. Robbed objects – metals, amulets, grave goods – thus entered circulation and could be reintroduced into the funerary market.

¹²Schneider, Hans D.: *Shabtis. An Introduction to the History of Ancient Egyptian Funerary Statuettes*. 3 Bde., Leiden: Rijksmuseum van Oudheden / Brill, 1977.

¹³Petrie, W. M. Flinders: *Shabtis*. London: British School of Archaeology in Egypt / Bernard Quaritch, 1914.

¹⁴Petrie, W. M. Flinders: *Shabtis*. London: British School of Archaeology in Egypt / Bernard Quaritch, 1914.

¹⁵Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

¹⁶Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

This circulation of objects forms the structural background for the phenomenon of usurpation of funerary goods: a robbed or clearance-derived ushabti need not be destroyed. If materially intact, it could be made serviceable for a new owner through renaming. The object retained its funerary efficacy – provided the new name was correctly inscribed and the formula was complete.

The 19th Dynasty: prosperity and stability as the context for UB-006

Within the Ramesside period, the 19th Dynasty (ca. 1295–1186 BCE) is a phase of relative political stability and economic prosperity. Under Seti I and Ramesses II, building activity was intensive; the necropoleis were expanded, and the priesthood grew. It was a time in which high-quality funerary objects were produced for the middle nobility and the priesthood alike – and in which demand for such objects was strong enough to make the reuse of existing pieces both economically rational and socially acceptable.

Schloegl's dating of UB-006 to the 19th Dynasty¹⁷ places the object in precisely the era in which the conditions for a usurpation such as that documented on this piece were in place in multiple respects: a well-developed funerary market, a priestly class as potential patron, craft expertise in painted terracotta, and a social acceptance of the reuse of funerary objects supported by economic logic.

Theban funerary contexts and the unknown findspot of UB-006

Most known usurped ushabtis derive from Theban necropoleis, or such a findspot is probable. The precise findspot of UB-006 is not known; it is secured by auction provenance from 1987, not by archaeological context.¹⁸ The attribution to the 19th Dynasty, the material group (red clay with white ground and polychrome decoration), and the character of the inscription with Book of the Dead Spell 6 are, however, consistent with Theban production centres of this period. A provenance from the West Theban area is therefore probable, without this conclusion being supported by archaeological certainty.

¹⁷Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

¹⁸Lempertz Auktion 622, Köln, 26.06.1987, Taf. 79, Nr. 1647.

Object Description and Inscription

UB-006 is a large mummiform ushabti made of red clay (terracotta) with a white ground layer and polychrome painted details in black, red, green and blue (see Fig. 2).

The figure shows careful surface preparation: the white ground layer is clearly distinguishable from the paint layer applied over it. Despite significant abrasion and partial paint loss, individual polychrome details on the wig and body remain visible. A break in the lower section has resulted in the loss of the end of the inscription.

Primary inscription (erased): The original, nearly encircling, five-line inscription painted in black was erased in antiquity. No secure information is available on the content of this primary text; only remnants were reused during the usurpation (see Fig. 3) (see Fig. 4).

Secondary inscription (usurpation): Within a red rectangular frame, parts of the earlier inscription were reused and supplemented with newly added signs in black. The orientation of anthropomorphic and zoomorphic signs (human figure, bird, eye) faces to the right; the inscription is therefore to be read from right to left (see Fig. 1).

Preserved sign sequence (schematic, right-to-left):

[Hieroglyphen: Q1 D4]

[Hieroglyphen: M17 X1 I9]

Securely identifiable elements:

- The divine name Osiris (Wsir), composed of the throne sign (Q1) and the eye (D4).
- The name of the usurper: Jt.f (jt=f, "his father"), as established by Schloegl.¹⁹
- Additional signs are fragmentary and in part difficult to determine due to abrasion or repainting.

According to Schloegl, the secondary inscription represents a short version of Book of the Dead Spell 6: "May Osiris It be illumined, O shabti, when one counts [him] to do any work that is to be done ..." The end of the text is lost due to the break in the lower section.²⁰

¹⁹Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

²⁰Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

Epigraphic Analysis

The epigraphic analysis of the secondary inscription of UB-006 forms the scholarly core of this study. The foundation is Hermann A. Schloegl's examination, documented in two stages: first in the Lempertz auction catalogue 622 (Cologne, 26 Jun 1987, pl. 79, no. 1647), and in expanded, confirmed form in Schloegl/Brodbeck (1990), catalogue no. 74.²¹ The present analysis additionally incorporates a comparison with recent detail photographs of the object.

The history of documentation: from auction catalogue to scholarly publication

A remarkable aspect of the research history of UB-006 is that the path from initial suspicion to confirmed scholarly conclusion is exemplarily traceable. In the Lempertz auction catalogue of 1987, the cataloguer noted cautiously: "The inscription has been altered, as the sign remnants at the edges of the frame clearly show. Whether ancient reuse?"²² – the question still open, but the observation already precisely formulated. It was Hermann A. Schloegl who acquired the object at this auction. On the basis of his own autopsy and scholarly examination of the piece, he published it three years later together with Andreas Brodbeck in Schloegl/Brodbeck (1990), under the catalogue title "Usurped funerary figure for It" and contains the complete epigraphic assessment.²³ This development illustrates how careful object examination – supported by renewed autopsy and the possibility of comparison – transformed into a secure scholarly conclusion through object examination and disciplinary expertise.

(see Fig. 5)

(see Fig. 6)

The primary inscription: erasure of a five-line body inscription

According to Schloegl, the original inscription of UB-006 was a nearly body-encircling, five-line inscription painted in black.²⁴ This arrangement – a near-complete wrapping of the body in inscribed text – corresponds to the design principle of high-quality ushabtis of the 19th Dynasty, on which the Book of the Dead Spell 6 formula was frequently distributed over several lines across the chest, abdomen, and back.

The primary inscription was erased entirely in antiquity. On the object, the erasure is visible through the uniform, freshly-appearing white of the ground layer in the area outside the red frame. The detail photographs show, however, that at the margins of the frame – particularly in the lateral border zones – trace remnants of the primary inscription have survived (see Fig. 3). No coherent sign sequences are legible; the remnants are too fragmentary to permit conclusions about the formula or the name of the original owner. It is precisely this testimony of incomplete erasure that is epigraphically significant: the sign remnants at the edges of the frame were what Schloegl recognised in 1987 as the first indication of the inscription's alteration.

The secondary inscription: structure and layout

The secondary inscription was applied within a red rectangular frame on the front of the figure (see Fig. 4) (see Fig. 2). The red frame line is clearly preserved at the upper edge; red vertical lines run downward along each side. This frame defines the inscription field and clearly demarcates it from the surrounding surface – now white and free of signs.

Within the frame, parts of the original inscription were reused and supplemented with newly added signs in black, according to Schloegl.²⁵ This is a particularly sophisticated approach: the usurper, or the scribe commissioned for the task, was not working on a completely cleared surface, but made use of existing sign elements from the primary

²¹Lempertz Auktion 622, Köln, 26.06.1987, Taf. 79, Nr. 1647.

Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

²²Lempertz Auktion 622, Köln, 26.06.1987, Taf. 79, Nr. 1647.

²³Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

²⁴Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

²⁵Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

inscription for the new composition. This principle of selective reuse presupposes that the primary inscription within the area of the red frame was only partially erased or overpainted – a method that is both economically and technically sensible, as it minimises the effort required.

The secondary inscription comprises five horizontal lines giving an abbreviated version of Book of the Dead Spell 6. The reading direction is right-to-left, as the orientation of anthropomorphic and zoomorphic signs clearly attests: human figure, bird, and eye all face to the right.

Analysis of individual signs: the usurper's name Jt.f

The epigraphically central finding is the name of the usurper, which Schloegl reads as Jt.f (jt=f, "his father").²⁶ The spelling follows the standard form of the name (Ranke I, 50,13) with the signs:

[Hieroglyphen: M17 X1 I9]

The reed leaf (M17, phonetic value i), the bread loaf (X1, phonetic value t), and the horned viper (I9, phonetic value f) together form the consonantal sequence j-t-f. Jt.f is attested as a personal name in the New Kingdom, though rarely. On the object, the name spelling is in places difficult to decipher due to the overlapping of the usurpation layers; Schloegl's reading is, however, secured through comparison with the drawing (see Fig. 1).

The ntr-sign and the title of the first owner: an epigraphic re-semanticisation

The most subtle and scientifically interesting aspect of the usurpation is described by Schloegl as follows: the ntr-sign (𓏏), which in the primary inscription had presumably formed part of the title it-ntr (God's Father) of the original owner, was incorporated into the divine name Wsir (Osiris) during the reworking.²⁷ The divine name Wsir is formed from:

[Hieroglyphen: Q1 D4]

The throne sign (Q1) and the eye (D4). Schloegl specifies: the ntr-sign now belongs to the divine name Osiris – adding the possibility that the original owner held the title God's Father (it-ntr).

This observation deserves particular attention. It demonstrates that the usurpation was not a schematic name-erasure and renewal, but an active, meaning-driven reinterpretation of the existing sign repertoire. The scribe recognised the possibility of transferring an existing sign – the ntr-sign belonging to the first owner – into a new semantic context suited to the new owner formula. This approach requires not only technical skill, but also a confident command of hieroglyphic sign semantics.

Book of the Dead Spell 6 in abbreviated form: textual reconstruction

The five preserved lines give, according to Schloegl, an abbreviated version of Book of the Dead Spell 6. The preserved formula reads approximately: "May Osiris It [Jt.f] be illumined, O shabti, when one counts him to do any work that is to be done ..."²⁸ The end of the text is lost due to the break in the lower section of the object (see Fig. 7).

Book of the Dead Spell 6 is the most frequently used text on ushabtis and contains in its complete form the summons to the figure to perform every task in the realm of the dead on behalf of the deceased when called upon – field work, irrigation, carrying sand. The abbreviated version present on UB-006 is limited to the opening illumination formula and the beginning of the task designation. Such abbreviations are frequently attested on Ramesside ushabtis and represent less a content limitation than a reflection of the pragmatic economy of inscription practice; the funerary efficacy of the object is not diminished.

The relationship between primary and secondary inscription: material evidence

The detail photographs permit several supplementary observations on the material evidence of the usurpation. In the

²⁶Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

²⁷Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

²⁸Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

side view of the figure (inscription_layering), faint sign remnants attributable to the primary inscription are visible in the transitional zone between the red-framed main inscription field and the lateral surfaces. Their contours are blurred and partially fragmented by the white overpainting – an indication that erasure was achieved by applying a new white ground layer, rather than through mechanical abrasion down to the clay body.

The red frame itself is applied with a regular brushwork and lies visibly above the white ground layer. The black secondary signs follow above it. This stratigraphic sequence – clay / ground layer / erasure layer / red frame / secondary inscription – is traceable at certain points on the object and supports Schloegl's interpretation of the process.

A full reconstruction of the primary formula is deliberately not attempted here. The surviving sign remnants are too fragmentary and too obscured by overpainting to permit reliable reading. Any reconstruction attempt would exceed the boundaries of the secure evidence.

Conclusion: the epigraphic significance of UB-006

UB-006 is a rare example of a well-documented and autopsy-confirmed usurpation on a painted terracotta ushabti. The combination of the preserved red frame, the still-discernible remnants of the primary inscription, the secure reading of the usurper's name, and the remarkable re-semanticisation of the ntr-sign makes the object an epigraphic specimen of high scholarly value. The two-stage documentation by Schloegl – from the cautious question of 1987 to the confirmed analysis of 1990 – further attests to the methodological rigour with which the object was approached.²⁹

²⁹Lempertz Auktion 622, Köln, 26.06.1987, Taf. 79, Nr. 1647.

Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: *Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz*. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

Technical Examination

The technical examination of UB-006 comprises UV fluorescence analysis under 365 nm in the form of a complete photographic documentation of all object surfaces (front, back, both sides, chest, base, and detail photographs of the entire inscription area). Raking-light photographs were additionally consulted for visual assessment of the layer structure. Further scientific analysis (Raman spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence, binding medium analysis, stratigraphic cross-section) has not yet been carried out. Requests for such investigations have been submitted to specialised laboratories; results will be published as an updated version of this publication upon receipt.

Methodological note: UV fluorescence photography (365 nm) is an established, non-destructive method for documenting surface modifications, retouching, and secondary reworking phases on painted surfaces. Different materials – pigments, binding media, ground layers – may fluoresce with varying intensity or absorb UV radiation under UV excitation. Conclusions regarding pigment identity or binding medium composition are not possible on the basis of photographic documentation alone; the observations are to be understood as indications that may motivate further analytical steps.

Overall appearance under UV (front and back)

The overall front view under UV shows the characteristic basic appearance (see Fig. 8) (see Fig. 9): the white ground layer fluoresces intensely in a uniform lavender to violet tone, while the black-painted hieroglyphs of the secondary inscription show virtually no fluorescence and stand out clearly as dark forms. The blue-painted wig fluoresces conspicuously in a strong blue – behaviour characteristic of Egyptian blue (cuprorivaite, $\text{CaCuSi}_2\text{O}_6$).

The back surface provides one of the most significant findings of the entire UV examination (see Fig. 10) (see Fig. 11): on the back of the body, in the central and upper back area, two clearly separated, horizontally running dark bands are discernible, setting themselves distinctly apart from the fluorescing ground. These are not decorative elements – the back of the ushabti carries no figural or ornamental painting. These bands are to be interpreted as remnants of the original primary inscription preserved beneath the covering layer, with their pigments remaining visible under UV through the overlying ground coat. This finding provides direct material support for Schloegl's description of a nearly body-encircling five-line primary inscription.³⁰ It simultaneously demonstrates that erasure was achieved by overpainting, not by mechanical abrasion down to the clay body.

Side views: primary inscription on both sides

The UV photographs of both sides confirm the picture of the encircling primary inscription (see Fig. 13) (see Fig. 13) (see Fig. 15) (see Fig. 15): on both sides of the body, in the lower body area, faint dark vertical traces are visible against the ground fluorescence. These traces are too fragmentary for epigraphic reading, but together with the back finding they form a consistent overall picture: the primary inscription did indeed run nearly around the entire body and was erased by overpainting on all surfaces.

The complete inscription column: the decisive overall finding

The complete UV photograph of the inscription column from top to bottom is the analytically most productive single image (see Fig. 16): it shows the five lines of the secondary inscription clearly and sharply set against the fluorescing ground. The decisive finding lies to the left of the red-framed secondary inscription field: over the entire height of the inscription column, vertical dark traces run here, remaining visible outside the red frame. These traces are located where the left side of the encircling primary inscription must have run. They were not completely suppressed by the covering layer and remain visible under UV. Together with the back finding and the lateral traces, a complete UV picture of the erasure operation emerges: the primary inscription was covered on the front face within the frame area by a new ground layer, and likewise outside the frame and on the back and side surfaces, though with varying thoroughness.

(see Fig. 17) (see Fig. 18)

Inscription area: detailed analysis of individual zones

³⁰Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

Upper inscription area: the red frame is clearly recognisable as a non-fluorescing, dark stripe (see Fig. 19). Immediately outside the frame, in the left margin zone, areas of slightly varying fluorescence intensity are visible – diffuse traces that may be interpreted as remnants of the primary inscription showing through beneath the covering layer.

Central inscription area: within the secondary inscription, zones of varying ground brightness alternate (see Fig. 20). This inhomogeneity is consistent with the presence of an erasure layer – a secondarily applied ground coat differing from the original in binding medium or layer thickness.

Lower inscription area and Wsir signs: the close-up of the lower inscription area with the Wsir signs (throne sign and eye) shows marked inhomogeneities of the ground fluorescence directly around and between the signs (see Fig. 21). The brownish-red patches that appear in raking light as exposed clay areas show under UV a clear demarcation from the fluorescing ground. This finding is consistent with an inhomogeneous erasure layer in which the ground has partially flaked away to expose the underlying clay.

Frame area: the close-up of the frame zone shows the frame line as a distinctly dark, non-fluorescing stripe (see Fig. 22). The ground fluorescence within the frame is observably more inhomogeneous than outside it – a finding consistent with a two-phase ground history. The frame line overlies the ground layer, attesting to its secondary application as part of the usurpation process.

Base area: documentation of repair

The UV photograph of the base area shows a pronounced green-cyan fluorescence at the adhesive repair (see Fig. 23). This characteristic green fluorescence is typical of various organic adhesives and consolidants, and precisely confirms and locates the repair documented in Schloegl/Brodbeck (1990).³¹

Chest area: original polychrome decoration

The UV photograph of the chest area shows the polychrome collar decoration with a differentiated UV response (see Fig. 24). The more uniform fluorescence of this area compared to the inscription column is an indication that the original ground layer is preserved here without secondary reworking.

Overall assessment: UV evidence for the usurpation

The complete UV documentation provides a consistent and internally coherent picture of the usurpation:³²

- The two horizontal dark bands on the back directly attest to the primary inscription on the side of the figure facing away from the viewer.
- The vertical traces on both sides of the body demonstrate that the primary inscription was indeed nearly body-encircling.
- The vertical traces to the left of the secondary inscription field on the front surface document where the primary inscription extended into the area of the later secondary text.
- The inhomogeneity of the ground fluorescence within the red frame is consistent with an erasure layer.
- The position of the red frame above the ground layer attests to its secondary application.
- The green fluorescence at the foot precisely locates the documented repair.

For definitive conclusions regarding stratigraphic sequence and material composition, cross-sections and material-analytical methods would be required. Taken as a whole, however, the UV findings provide a material confirmation of the epigraphically postulated usurpation that goes beyond mere compatibility.

³¹Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

³²Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

Comparative Catalogue

The following brief overview lists published ushabtis with confirmed or probable ancient usurpation that can be used as comparative material for UB-006. A systematic catalogue of all known usurped ushabtis has not yet been produced in the research literature; the objects listed here represent a selection based on accessible collection databases and auction records.

British Museum EA33947 – Shabti of Pashed (19th Dynasty, painted ceramic): The piece shows red dividing lines between the inscription registers, a structurally related design to the red framing in UB-006.³³ Ancient usurpation is not documented for this example; it serves as a typological comparative object.

British Museum EA15760 – Shabti of Hat (19th Dynasty, painted ceramic): White ground with polychrome painting, comparable in colouring and material group.³⁴ No documented usurpation; typological parallel.

Hood Museum of Art (Dartmouth) 39.64.6628 – Shabti of Sebekmose (19th Dynasty, painted ceramic): Similar proportions, material, and chromatic effect; no documented usurpation.³⁵

KV62 (Tomb of Tutankhamun, 18th Dynasty, c. 1323 BCE) – Selected reassigned grave goods: Several objects from the inventory of the best-known tomb discovery in Egyptology show confirmed or highly probable traces of ancient reassignment. The four miniature golden canopic coffins (Carter nos. 266a–d) bear, beneath Tutankhamun’s cartouches, reconstructable inscriptions of Neferneferuaten, including the gender-specific epithet Axt-n-H(j)=s; the pectoral of the goddess Nut was originally made for Neferneferuaten and altered only in its cartouches; the golden death mask bears, according to Reeves and Gabolde, palimpsest traces of an earlier cartouche pointing to Ankhkheperure Neferneferuaten as the original owner.³⁶ The motive was not economic but logistical in nature: the unexpected death of the young king forced those responsible to draw on available material within the ritual burial deadline of approximately 70–90 days. The incomplete and inconsistent character of the overwritings – iconographic substance largely untouched, only the name fields altered – excludes a politically motivated *damnatio memoriae* and firmly assigns the interventions to pragmatic reuse. As a broader comparative example, KV62 differs fundamentally from UB-006 in social register, material value, and dynastic context; at the phenomenological level – pragmatic reassignment of a funerarily activated object without hostile intent toward the original owner – the structural analogy is nevertheless evident.³⁷

Gorny & Mosch Auction 312, Lot 8 (2025): The object UB-006 itself was offered under the title “Usurped shabti of It”, documenting the usurpation as an identifying characteristic in the collection and market context.³⁸

Research desideratum: A comprehensive catalogue of usurped ushabtis systematically incorporating museum databases (British Museum, Metropolitan Museum, Louvre, Rijksmuseum van Oudheden), auction archives, and unpublished collection holdings would constitute a significant contribution to the study of this phenomenon. UB-006 could serve as a documented anchor point for such a catalogue.

³³British Museum, EA33947 (Shabti of Pashed; painted pottery; 19. Dynastie).
https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA33947

³⁴British Museum, EA15760 (Shabti of Hat; painted pottery; 19. Dynastie).
https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA15760

³⁵Hood Museum of Art (Dartmouth), 39.64.6628 (Shabti of Sebekmose; pottery with paint; 19. Dynastie).
<https://hoodmuseum.dartmouth.edu/objects/39.64.6628>

³⁶Reeves, Nicholas: The Gold Mask of Ankhkheperure Neferneferuaten. In: Göttinger *Miszellen* 247 (2015), S. 71–75. [Bitte Seitenangaben vor Drucklegung anhand des Originals verifizieren.]

Gabolde, Marc: *D’Akhenaton à Toutânkhamon*. Lyon: Université Lumière-Lyon 2, 1998. (Collection de l’Institut d’Archéologie et d’Histoire de l’Antiquité, 3).

³⁷Reeves, Nicholas: The Gold Mask of Ankhkheperure Neferneferuaten. In: Göttinger *Miszellen* 247 (2015), S. 71–75. [Bitte Seitenangaben vor Drucklegung anhand des Originals verifizieren.]

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Eaton-Krauss, Marianne: *The Unknown Tutankhamun*. London / New York: Bloomsbury Academic, 2016.

³⁸Gorny & Mosch Giessener Münzhandlung, Auktion 312, 04.07.2025, Los 8: “Usurped shabti of It”.
<https://auktionen.gmcoinart.de/Auktion/KatalogArchiv?intAuktionsId=1595>

Provenance

Provenance event [1]: Unknown ownership until 26 Jun 1987.

Provenance event [2]: Acquired on 26 Jun 1987 by Hermann A. Schloegl at Lempertz (Cologne), Auction 622, Lot 1647.³⁹

Provenance event [3]: Acquired on 04 Jul 2025 by Dirk Beckers from Gorny & Mosch, Auction 312, Lot 8.⁴⁰

³⁹Lempertz Auktion 622, Köln, 26.06.1987, Taf. 79, Nr. 1647.

⁴⁰Gorny & Mosch Giessener Münzhandlung, Auktion 312, 04.07.2025, Los 8: "Usurped shabti of It".
<https://auktionen.gmcoinart.de/Auktion/KatalogArchiv?intAuktionsId=1595>

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- British Museum, EA33947.⁴⁴
- British Museum, EA15760.⁴⁵
- Hood Museum of Art (Dartmouth), 39.64.6628.⁴⁶
- Lempertz Auktionshaus, Auction 622, Cologne 1987, pl. 79, no. 1647.⁴⁷
- Gorny & Mosch Giessener Muenzhandlung, Auction 312 (04 Jul 2025), Lot 8.⁴⁸

⁴¹Schlögl, Hermann Alexander / Brodbeck, Andreas: Ägyptische Totenfiguren aus öffentlichen und privaten Sammlungen der Schweiz. Zürich: Universität Zürich, 1990, Katalog Nr. 74, S. 135.

⁴²Petrie, W. M. Flinders: Shabtis. London: British School of Archaeology in Egypt / Bernard Quaritch, 1914.

⁴³Schneider, Hans D.: Shabtis. An Introduction to the History of Ancient Egyptian Funerary Statuettes. 3 Bde., Leiden: Rijksmuseum van Oudheden / Brill, 1977.

⁴⁴British Museum, EA33947 (Shabti of Pashed; painted pottery; 19. Dynastie).
https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA33947

⁴⁵British Museum, EA15760 (Shabti of Hat; painted pottery; 19. Dynastie).
https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA15760

⁴⁶Hood Museum of Art (Dartmouth), 39.64.6628 (Shabti of Sebekmose; pottery with paint; 19. Dynastie).
<https://hoodmuseum.dartmouth.edu/objects/39.64.6628>

⁴⁷Lempertz Auktion 622, Köln, 26.06.1987, Taf. 79, Nr. 1647.

⁴⁸Gorny & Mosch Giessener Münzhandlung, Auktion 312, 04.07.2025, Los 8: "Usurped shabti of It".
<https://auktionen.gmcoinart.de/Auktion/KatalogArchiv?intAuktionsId=1595>

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Figure 1: Red name field of the secondary inscription on UB-006

Figure 2: Front view of UB-006 showing inscription area

Figure 3: Inscription layering: traces of the primary and secondary inscription

Figure 4: Upper inscription area with traces of the primary inscription

Inschrift: Aufgemalt. Die ursprünglich fast um den Körper herumführende, fünfzeilige, schwarz aufgemalte Inschrift ist antik gelöscht. In ein rotes Rechteck eingeschlossen wurden Teile dieser Inschrift wiederverwendet, dabei aber auch neue Zeichen in Schwarz hinzugefügt. Der Name des Usurpators muss als 'Jt.f' gelesen werden, und das ntr-Zeichen gehört jetzt zum Gottesnamen Osiris (vielleicht hatte der Erstbesitzer den Titel 'Gottesvater'). Die jetzigen fünf waagrechten Zeilen geben eine Kurzform von Tb-Spruch 6: *Es werde beschienen Osiris It, o Schabti, wenn man abzählt, um irgend eine Arbeit zu machen ...* Der Rest ist durch den Bruch zerstört.

Figure 5: Schloegl's commentary on the inscription (Lempertz 1987)

Figure 6: Hieroglyphic drawing of the inscription after Schloegl (Schloegl/Brodbeck 1990)

Figure 7: Base area with break and repair

Figure 8: UV overall view, front (365 nm)

Figure 9: UV overall view, front, second photograph

Figure 10: UV rear view, first photograph

Figure 11: UV rear view, second photograph

Figure 12: UV side view, left, first photograph

Figure 13: UV side view, left, second photograph

Figure 14: UV side view, right, first photograph

Figure 15: UV side view, right, second photograph

Figure 16: UV overall view, inscription column complete (365 nm)

Figure 17: UV detail, central and lower inscription area

Figure 18: UV overall view, inscription column, second photograph

Figure 19: UV detail, upper inscription area

Figure 20: UV detail, central inscription area

Figure 21: UV detail, lower inscription area with Wsir signs

Figure 22: UV detail, frame zone

Figure 23: UV detail, base area

Figure 24: UV detail, chest area